

Translational neuroimaging of cerebral perfusion after acute ischemic stroke

Supplementary material

Contents

Chapter 2	2
Chapter 3	7
Chapter 4	21
Chapter 5	25
Chapter 6	27
Chapter 7	29

Chapter 2

Implications of post-recanalization perfusion deficit after acute ischemic stroke – A scoping review of clinical and preclinical imaging studies

Supplementary Table 1: Study-specific reperfusion pattern and outcome in AIS patients on time points after stroke onset.

Study (subgroup level if applicable)	N	Treatment	Perfusion imaging method	Primary outcome measure	5-18h	<12h	12-24h	24h	24-36h	48h	3d	4d	7d	9d	1m
SPONTANEOUS REPERFUSION AND NEUTRAL OUTCOME															
Liu et al. [84]	27	None	DSC-MRI	HT, BBB leakage		Norm			Norm	Norm	Hyper	Hyper	Hyper	Hyper	Norm
SPONTANEOUS REPERFUSION AND FAVORABLE OUTCOME															
Marchal et al. [9]	18	None	PET	2m MCASS and EI	Hyper										
Marchal et al. [14]	30	None	PET	2m MCASS and RI	Hyper										Norm
Crisi et al. [44]	47	None	ASL	6m NIHSS					Hyper						
TREATMENT AND NO (INTERPRETABLE) RELATION TO OUTCOME															
Ter Schiphorst et al. [26]	33	EVT	ASL	3m mRS					Hyper						
Brugnara et al. [93]	47	EVT	CTP	None	Hyper										
TREATMENT AND NEUTRAL OUTCOME															
Kidwell et al. [47]	12	IVT	DSC-MRI	3m mRS	Hyper								Hyper		
TREATMENT AND FAVORABLE OUTCOME															
Viallon et al. [45]	41	Antiplatelet or IVT	ASL and DSC-MRI	mRS						Hyper					
Bivard et al. [46]	100	IVT	ASL	3m mRS				Hyper							
Bivard et al. [39]	77	IVT	ASL	3m mRS				Hyper							
Yu et al. [48]	221	Miscellaneous	ASL	HT		Hyper									
Bhaskar et al. [43]	119	IVT	ASL	3m mRS			Hyper								
Lu et al. [40]	54	EVT	ASL	3m mRS								Hyper			
Potreck et al. [41]	38	EVT or EVT and IVT	DSC-MRI	3m mRS				Hyper							
Rosso et al. [25] (H/H & H/N profile)	226	IVT	ASL	3m mRS				Hyper							
TREATMENT AND UNFAVORABLE OUTCOME															
Yu et al. [48]	221	Miscellaneous	ASL	HT			Hyper								
Okazaki et al. [82]	31	IVT or EVT, or both	ASL	HT							Hyper				
Kosior et al. 2017 [49]	50	EVT	DSAP	HT					Hyper						
Shimonaga et al. [42]	27	EVT	ASL	3m mRS					Hyper						
Rubiera et al. [32]	151	EVT	CTP	3m mRS	Hyper										
Ng et al. [24]	130	IVT or IVT and EVT	DSC-MRI	3m mRS				Hyper							
Rosso et al. [25] (h/h profile)	226	IVT	ASL	3m mRS				Hyper							

Hyper indicates hyperperfusion; Norm, normoperfusion; Hypo, hypoperfusion; H/H, hyperperfusion in- and outside the lesion; H/N, hyperperfusion inside and normoperfusion outside the lesion; h/h: hypoperfusion in- and outside the lesion; IVT, intravenous thrombolysis; EVT, endovascular thrombectomy; PET, positron emission tomography; ASL, arterial spin labeling; DSC-MRI, dynamic susceptibility contrast-enhanced magnetic resonance imaging; DSAP, Digital Subtraction Angiography Perfusion; CTP, computed tomography perfusion; MCASS, middle cerebral artery stroke scale; EI, Martinez-Vila's evolution indices; RI, recovery index; mRS, modified Rankin Scale; NIHSS, National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale; HT, hemorrhagic transformation incidence; BBB, blood-brain barrier.

Supplementary Table 2: Study-specific reperfusion pattern and outcome in AIS animal models on time points after occlusion.

Study (subgroup level if applicable)	Animal	N	Occlusion duration (min)	Perfusion imaging method	Region of interest	Outcome measure	0-15 min	30 min	1h	1-2h	2-3h	3-6h	12h	1d	2d	3d	4d	5d	6d	7d	14d	21d	28d			
NO OUTCOME REPORTED																										
Van Dorsten et al. [54]	Mouse	6	60	ASL	Anatomically driven ROIs	NA		Hypo	Hypo	Hypo				Hypo												
Li et al. [67]	Rat	8	30	DSC-MRI (CBF)	Anatomically driven ROIs	NA	Norm	Norm	Norm	Norm			Norm	Norm	Norm	Norm										
Van Dorsten et al. [55]	Rat	20	60	ASL	Various ADC-derived thresholds	NA	Norm	Norm	Hypo	Hypo	Hypo	Norm														
Van Dorsten et al. [55]	Rat		90	ASL	Various ADC-derived thresholds	NA	Hyper	Norm	Hypo	Norm	Norm	Norm														
Lin et al. [61]	Rat	108 (k=14)	60	ASL and DSC-MRI (CBF and CBV)	Anatomically driven ROIs	NA						Norm		Hyper		Hyper		Hyper		Hyper	Hyper					
Tanaka et al. [65]	Rat	6	60	ASL and DSC-MRI (CBF)	Anatomically and CBF driven ROIs	NA				Hyper					Hyper											
Martín et al. [59]	Rat	52	120	PET and SPECT	MCA irrigation territory	NA								Hypo	Norm		Hyper				Hyper					
Martín et al. [60]	Rat	7	120	PET	MCA irrigation territory and anatomically driven ROIs	NA								Hypo		Norm					Hyper	Norm	Norm	Norm		
NEUTRAL OUTCOME																										
Wegener et al. [64] (reperfusion pattern A)	Rat	8	60	ASL	PWI-derived lesion	Neurological score								Hypo / Norm			Hyper						Hyper			
Wegener et al. [64] (reperfusion pattern B)	Rat		60	ASL	PWI-derived lesion	Neurological score									Hyper			Hyper						Hyper / Norm		
Wegener et al. [64] (reperfusion pattern C)	Rat		60	ASL	PWI-derived lesion	Neurological score									Hyper			Hyper / Norm						Hyper / Norm		
FAVORABLE OUTCOME																										

Chapter 3

Hyperperfusion profiles after recanalization differentially associate with outcome in a rat ischemic stroke model

Supplementary figure I. Empirical cumulative density functions (ECDF) of the (post-)ischemic area and contralesional homologue in male rats. Voxels in the (post-)ischemic area and contralesional homologue of cerebral blood flow, cerebral blood volume and mean transit time maps (rows) during 90- or 45-min MCA occlusion, 0.5h post-recanalization and four days post-recanalization (columns) were repercentaged to a reference value, the contralateral median. ECDFs were then calculated of all repercentaged values of these areas per time point. The ECDF is associated with the empirical measure of a sample: the value of the color gradient at any specified value of the measured variable along the abscissa is the fraction of observations that are less than or equal to that specified value. Representative perfusion maps from the same male subject are displayed at the top-right corner of each cell. CL=contralesional, IL=ipsilesional, rrCBF = relative regional cerebral blood flow (rrCBF), rrCBV = relative regional cerebral blood volume, rrMTT = relative regional mean transit time.

Supplementary figure II. Empirical cumulative density functions (ECDF) of the (post-)ischemic area and contralesional homologue in female rats. Voxels in the (post-)ischemic area and contralesional homologue of cerebral blood flow, cerebral blood volume and mean transit time maps (rows) during 90- or 45-min MCA occlusion, 0.5h post-recanalization and four days post-recanalization (columns) were repercentaged to a reference value, the contralateral median. ECDFs were then calculated of all repercentaged values of these areas per time point. The ECDF is associated with the empirical measure of a sample: the value of the color gradient at any specified value of the measured variable along the abscissa is the fraction of observations that are less than or equal to that specified value. Representative perfusion maps from the same female subject are displayed at the top-right corner of each cell. CL=contralesional, IL=ipsilesional, rrCBF = relative regional cerebral blood flow (rrCBF), rrCBV = relative regional cerebral blood volume, rrMTT = relative regional mean transit time.

Supplementary Figure III. Histopathological features of brain infarction on hematoxylin-eosin-stained sections. **a)** Hemorrhage with abundant erythrocytes in the center of the image. Loss of both eosinophilia and nuclei can be observed in the areas marked with ‘*’. Scale bar represents 50 μm . **b)** Representative image of infarcted tissue with numerous presence of red neurons (black arrows) together with extracellular edema/vacuolization (#). Scale bar represents 50 μm . **c)** A zone with extracellular edema/vacuolization (#), in which light-blue arrows point to cells with nuclear abnormalities. Scale bar represents 25 μm .

Supplementary Table I – Sensorimotor deficit score (SDS) test items

<p>a) Gait disturbances in open area during one minute (0-5)</p>	<p>0. Straight walking; 1. Walking towards paretic side; 2. Alternate circling and walking straight; 3. Alternate circling and walking towards paretic side; 4. Circling and/or other gait disturbance (backing, crawling, walking on digits); 5. Constant circling towards paretic side.</p>
<p>b) Motility during one minute (0-5)</p>	<p>0. Normal exploratory behavior; 1. Slightly reduced exploratory behavior; 2. Moving limbs without proceeding; 3. Moving only to stimuli; 4. Unresponsive to stimuli, with normal muscle tone; 5. Severely decreased tone, premortal signs.</p>
<p>c) Lateral resistance (0-2)</p>	<p>0. When pushed lateral, resistance equilateral; 1. When pushed lateral, less resistance in paretic direction; 2. When pushed lateral, no resistance in paretic direction.</p>
<p>d) Forelimb placing tests</p>	<p>I. Placement response when the contralateral vibrissae are stimulated (0-2) 0. Normal; 1. Weak (tries but doesn't manage to put paw on table); 2. Absent (does not respond to stimulation). II. Placement response when the ipsilateral vibrissae are stimulated (0-2) 0. Normal; 1. Weak (tries but doesn't manage to put paw on table); 2. Absent (does not respond to stimulation).</p>
<p>e) Forelimb reflexes after touching</p>	<p>I. Symmetry of grasping reflex of forepaw onto a rod when slightly touched (0-1) 0. Symmetrical (also applies if both sides function and alternate when trying multiple times) 1. Asymmetrical (one paw doesn't go to the rod when touched) II. Symmetry of strength, releasing tension when withdrawn for wire or rod (0-1) 0. Symmetrical; 1. Asymmetrical (when hanging from a rod 1 paw releases)</p>
<p>f) Postural signs (when held by tail base)</p>	<p>I. Degree of thorax twisting to one side (0-2) 0. No thorax twisting (hanging vertically); 1. Light thorax twisting; 2. Heavy thorax twisting. II. Degree of forelimb flexion towards contra-lateral side (0-2) 0. No forelimb flexion; 1. Light forelimb flexion; 2. Heavy forelimb flexion.</p>

Supplementary Table II – Acute ischemic tissue volume, subacute infarct volume and region-of-interest volumes, expressed as hemispheric volume fraction and % of acute ischemic lesion volume

	Female, 45min (N=9)	Male, 45min (N=12)	Female, 90min (N=10)	Male, 90min (N=11)
Acute ischemic volume				
Mean (SD)	0.203 (0.094)	0.180 (0.107)	0.141 (0.082)	0.151 (0.102)
Range	0.063 - 0.362	0.041 - 0.363	0.041 - 0.267	0.046 - 0.345
Subacute infarct volume				
Mean (SD)	0.123 (0.083)	0.175 (0.142)	0.130 (0.106)	0.171 (0.150)
Range	0.029 - 0.297	0.010 - 0.452	0.013 - 0.316	0.028 - 0.430
Lesion core				
Mean (SD)	0.107 (0.071)	0.143 (0.107)	0.106 (0.084)	0.126 (0.106)
Range	0.024 - 0.251	0.010 - 0.315	0.012 - 0.249	0.023 - 0.319
Salvageable tissue				
Mean (SD)	0.096 (0.060)	0.037 (0.020)	0.035 (0.013)	0.025 (0.012)
Range	0.029 - 0.201	0.006 - 0.069	0.018 - 0.057	0.012 - 0.047
Delayed injury				
Mean (SD)	0.015 (0.014)	0.033 (0.042)	0.024 (0.023)	0.045 (0.055)
Range	0.004 - 0.046	0.000 - 0.137	0.001 - 0.067	0.005 - 0.181
Rel. subacute infarct volume (%)				
Mean (SD)	57.4 (23.2)	85.1 (33.6)	78.6 (31.3)	99.1 (35.3)
Range	29.9 - 105.9	24.0 - 139.0	32.1 - 118.2	49.8 - 174.1
Rel. lesion core (%)				
Mean (SD)	50.2 (19.8)	69.6 (22.3)	64.7 (22.4)	74.0 (18.9)
Range	26.5 - 89.5	23.8 - 97.9	28.5 - 93.1	41.0 - 94.8
Rel. salvageable tissue (%)				
Mean (SD)	49.8 (19.8)	30.4 (22.3)	35.3 (22.4)	26.0 (19.0)
Range	10.5 - 73.5	2.1 - 76.2	6.9 - 71.5	5.2 - 59.4
Rel. delayed injury (%)				
Mean (SD)	7.2 (4.1)	15.5 (14.0)	13.9 (10.0)	25.1 (21.2)
Range	2.9 - 16.4	0.2 - 42.1	3.2 - 28.5	7.4 - 80.9

Supplementary Table III – Summary of main effects per perfusion index from linear mixed model analyses

Term	F	df	Residual df	<i>p</i>
Cerebral blood flow				
tMCAO (90min)	0.29	1	37.44	0.59
Sex (M)	8.44	1	37.25	0.006
Time	149.24	2	73.05	< 0.001
tMCAO:Sex	0.11	1	37.27	0.74
tMCAO:Time	0.17	2	73.24	0.85
Sex:Time	3.51	2	73.1	0.035
tMCAO:Sex:Time	1.02	2	73.15	0.37
Cerebral blood volume				
tMCAO (90min)	2.01	1	37.34	0.16
Sex (M)	9.7	1	37.14	0.004
Time	66.2	2	73.21	< 0.001
tMCAO:Sex	0.07	1	37.18	0.79
tMCAO:Time	0.87	2	73.4	0.42
Sex:Time	1.55	2	73.24	0.22
tMCAO:Sex:Time	0.25	2	73.29	0.78
Mean transit time				
tMCAO (90min)	0.48	1	37.25	0.49
Sex (M)	0.33	1	37.05	0.57
Time	279.94	2	73.34	< 0.001
tMCAO:Sex	0.02	1	37.09	0.89
tMCAO:Time	0.21	2	73.52	0.81
Sex:Time	0.58	2	73.36	0.56
tMCAO:Sex:Time	0.28	2	73.4	0.76
<i>Abbreviation:</i>			Note: residual degrees of freedom (df) are Kenward-Roger approximations	
<i>tMCAO: transient middle cerebral artery occlusion</i>				

Supplementary table IV – Post-hoc analyses of cerebral perfusion indices before and after recanalization

Sex	Time	Contrast	Estimate	Effect size	SE	Residual df	t	p
Cerebral blood flow								
.	1	M-F	0.58	0.02	9.09	106.82	0.06	> 0.99
.	2	M-F	17.36	0.63	9.09	106.82	1.91	0.41
.	3	M-F	33.56	1.23	9.31	107.25	3.61	0.003
F	.	2-1	53.48	1.95	8.9	71.57	6.01	< 0.001
F	.	3-2	34.91	1.27	8.9	71.57	3.92	0.001
M	.	2-1	70.26	2.57	8.29	71.57	8.48	< 0.001
M	.	3-2	51.11	1.87	8.56	76.65	5.97	< 0.001
Cerebral blood volume								
.	1	M-F	3.81	0.17	7.25	108.57	0.53	> 0.99
.	2	M-F	16.75	0.74	7.25	108.57	2.31	0.16
.	3	M-F	20.88	0.93	7.43	108.66	2.81	0.041
F	.	2-1	22.84	1.01	7.32	71.67	3.12	0.018
F	.	3-2	26.17	1.16	7.32	71.67	3.57	0.004
M	.	2-1	35.77	1.59	6.83	71.67	5.24	< 0.001
M	.	3-2	30.3	1.34	7.02	76.89	4.31	< 0.001
Mean transit time								
.	1	M-F	5.15	0.17	9.67	109	0.53	> 0.99
.	2	M-F	-6.9	-0.22	9.67	109	-0.71	> 0.99
.	3	M-F	-8.27	-0.27	9.91	109	-0.83	> 0.99
F	.	2-1	-125.86	-4.09	10.01	71.77	-12.58	< 0.001
F	.	3-2	-13.92	-0.45	10.01	71.77	-1.39	> 0.99
M	.	2-1	-137.91	-4.48	9.32	71.77	-14.79	< 0.001
M	.	3-2	-15.28	-0.5	9.57	77.06	-1.6	0.8

Abbreviations:

M: male; F: female. Times 1, 2 and 3 indicate relative experimental times: during MCAO (1), 0.5h post-recanalization (2) and 4 days post-recanalization (3)

Note: residual degrees of freedom (df) are Kenward-Roger approximations

Supplementary table V – Coefficients and performance measures for models with different configurations of perfusion parameters regressed against sensorimotor deficit score and ranked by performance (AICc)

	Models (ranking)					
	rrMTT (1)	$-DSC-PWI$ (2)	rrCBF & rrCBV (3)	rrCBV (4)	rrCBF (5)	<i>NULL</i> (6)
rrCBF			0.3* (0.01, 0.6)		-0.01 (-0.2, 0.1)	
rrCBV			-0.4* (-0.7, -0.1)	-0.1 (-0.3, 0.04)		
rrMTT	-0.2* (-0.3, -0.01)					
tMCAO (90min.)	0.4 [#] (-0.004, 0.8)	0.5* (0.1, 0.9)	0.5* (0.1, 0.9)	0.5* (0.1, 0.9)	0.5* (0.1, 0.9)	
Sex (M)	0.1 (-0.3, 0.5)	0.2 (-0.2, 0.6)	0.3 (-0.1, 0.7)	0.3 (-0.1, 0.7)	0.2 (-0.2, 0.6)	
Acute ischemic volume	0.3** (0.1, 0.5)	0.4** (0.2, 0.6)	0.3** (0.1, 0.5)	0.4** (0.2, 0.6)	0.4** (0.2, 0.6)	
Subcortical lesion	0.3 (-0.2, 0.7)	0.3 (-0.1, 0.8)	0.2 (-0.3, 0.7)	0.2 (-0.2, 0.7)	0.3 (-0.1, 0.8)	
Diencephalic lesion	-1.0** (-1.7, -0.4)	-1.0** (-1.7, -0.4)	-1.1** (-1.8, -0.5)	-1.1** (-1.7, -0.5)	-1.0** (-1.7, -0.4)	
tMCAO:Sex	-0.3 (-0.8, 0.3)	-0.3 (-0.8, 0.2)	-0.4 (-0.9, 0.1)	-0.4 (-0.9, 0.1)	-0.3 (-0.8, 0.2)	

Supplementary table V (continued)

Model performance	AICc	228	229.2	229.2	230	232.2	278.7
	X	4.33	0	6.37	2.26	0.03	
	$p (>X_{-DSC-PWI})$	0.04	1	0.04	0.13	0.85	
	RMSE	3	3.1	2.9	3	3.1	4.3
	Residual df	33	34	32	33	33	40
	Adjusted R ² (Nagelkerke)	0.84	0.82	0.85	0.83	0.82	0

Note: Models were tested against the base model without perfusion indices (\neg DSC-PWI), which included only tMCAO, sex and nuisance variables # $p < .10$; * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$

Abbreviations: tMCAO: transient middle cerebral artery occlusion. rrCBF: relative regional cerebral blood flow. rrCBV: relative regional cerebral blood volume. rrMTT: relative regional mean transit time. AICc: corrected Akaike information criterion, RMSE: root mean square error.

Supplementary table VI – Acute post-ischemic ADC (instead of relative regional perfusion), occlusion duration, sex and control variables regressed against lesion volume change or SDS

		<i>Dependent variable:</i>	
		<i>Lesion volume change</i>	<i>Sensorimotor deficit score</i>
Assumed distribution of dependent variable:		Normal	Poisson
Model coefficients (standardized β (± 95 CI))	0.5h ADC	-15.31** (-25.33, -5.29)	-0.21** (-0.38, -0.05)
	tMCAO (90min.)	5.55 (-21.12, 32.21)	0.10 (-0.39, 0.59)
	Sex (M)	16.69 (-4.19, 37.58)	-0.002 (-0.40, 0.40)
	Acute ischemic volume	6.19 (-6.12, 18.50)	0.27* (0.05, 0.49)
	Subcortical lesion	-27.83# (-52.93, -2.72)	0.22 (-0.24, 0.69)
	Diencephalic lesion	-27.96* (-53.27, -2.65)	-1.01** (-1.64, -0.38)
	tMCAO:Sex	-0.62 (-28.97, 27.72)	-0.16 (-0.69, 0.36)
Model performance	F	9.25	
	Log Likelihood		-105.97
	RMSE	19.6	2.97
	Residual df	34	34
	Adjusted R ²	0.58	
	Adjusted R ² (Nagelkerke)		0.87

Abbreviations: ADC: apparent diffusion coefficient. CI: confidence interval. RMSE: root mean square error.

#p < .10; * p < .05; ** p < .01

Supplementary table VI – Acute post-ischemic ADC (instead of relative regional perfusion), occlusion duration, sex and control variables regressed against lesion volume change or SDS

		<i>Dependent variable:</i>	
		<i>Lesion volume change</i>	<i>Sensorimotor deficit score</i>
Assumed distribution of dependent variable:		Normal	Poisson
Model coefficients (standardized β (± 95 CI))	0.5h ADC	-15.31** (-25.33, -5.29)	-0.21** (-0.38, -0.05)
	tMCAO (90min.)	5.55 (-21.12, 32.21)	0.10 (-0.39, 0.59)
	Sex (M)	16.69 (-4.19, 37.58)	-0.002 (-0.40, 0.40)
	Acute ischemic volume	6.19 (-6.12, 18.50)	0.27* (0.05, 0.49)
	Subcortical lesion	-27.83 [#] (-52.93, -2.72)	0.22 (-0.24, 0.69)
	Diencephalic lesion	-27.96* (-53.27, -2.65)	-1.01** (-1.64, -0.38)
	tMCAO:Sex	-0.62 (-28.97, 27.72)	-0.16 (-0.69, 0.36)
Model performance	F	9.25	
	Log Likelihood		-105.97
	RMSE	19.6	2.97
	Residual df	34	34
	Adjusted R ²	0.58	
	Adjusted R ² (Nagelkerke)		0.87

Abbreviations: ADC: apparent diffusion coefficient. CI: confidence interval. RMSE: root mean square error.

[#]p < .10; * p < .05; ** p < .01

Chapter 4

Molecular MRI of vascular inflammation after recanalization in a rat ischemic stroke model: MRI of vascular inflammation after ischemic stroke

Figure S1. Specificity of VCAM-1 molecular MRI at 24h post-recanalization. **A.** Coronal sections of susceptibility-weighted images before and after intravenous injection of VCAM-1-specific MPIO contrast agent (MPIO- α VCAM-1) or MPIO functionalized with the isotype control antibody (MPIO-IgG). Red arrowheads indicate MPIO accumulations. **B.** Mean signal void values in the lesion core area at 24h post-recanalization after intravenous injection of MPIO-IgG (n=3) or MPIO- α VCAM-1 (n=5). * p <0.05.

Figure S2. Representative cerebral blood flow (CBF), cerebral blood volume (CBV) and mean transit time (MTT) maps at 6h and 24h post-recanalization (left columns). The mean values of relative CBF, relative CBV and relative MTT (% of contralateral) are shown for different time-points after recanalization (right column). $n=4$ for 1h and 6h, $n=7$ for 24h, $n=3$ for 96h. * $p<0.05$ and # $p<0.1$.

Figure S3. Conventional box and whisker plots of cerebral blood flow (A), cerebral blood volume (B), and mean transit time (C) measured from the ipsilesional and homologous contralesional regions of interest (ROI). Pairwise *t*-tests were performed to test for significant differences between each hemisphere's ROI per time point. Sample size for each time point is represented at the top. ** $p < .01$; * $p < .05$

Chapter 5

Propofol anesthesia improves stroke outcomes over isoflurane anesthesia – a longitudinal multiparametric MRI study in a rodent model of transient middle cerebral artery occlusion

Supplementary Table 1: MRI pulse sequence data

	DWI	T_{2w}	DSC-MRI	Look-Locker	BOLD-MRI
Sequence	2D SE-EPI (8-shot)	2D SE-EPI (8-shot)	2D GE-EPI (single-shot)	2D GE-EPI (8-shot)	2D SE-EPI (single-shot)
TR / [TE] (ms)	2000 / [31]	3000 / [30, 50, 80, 190]	164 / [13]	5000 / [9]	705 / [4]
TI (ms)	20	20	15	[16 ... 4616] (24 equidistant echoes)	15
FOV	33.75 × 33.75 mm ²	33.75 × 33.75 mm ²	31.2 × 31.2 mm ²	33.6 × 33.6 mm ²	31.2 × 31.2 mm ²
Data matrix size	224 × 224 (25 slices)	224 × 224 (25 slices)	64 × 64 (6 slices)	128 × 128 (15 slices)	72 × 72 (13 slices)
Voxel size (μm³)	150 × 150 × 600	150 × 150 × 600	487.5 × 487.5 × 1200	262.5 × 262.5 × 1200	433.3 × 433.3 × 1200
Other	b = 0, 1454 s/mm ²		0.6 mm slice gap		

Note: DWI = diffusion-weighted imaging. T_{2w} = T₂-weighted imaging. DSC-MRI = dynamic susceptibility contrast-enhanced MRI. BOLD = blood oxygenation level dependent. FOV = field of view.

Chapter 6

Dynamics of cerebral blood volume during and after middle cerebral artery occlusion in rats - comparison between ultrafast ultrasound and dynamic susceptibility contrast-enhanced MRI measurements

Supplementary Figure 1. DSC-MRI demonstrates hypoperfusion during and after MCA occlusion. **(a)** Lack of perfusion in the ipsilesional hemisphere as shown by raw CBV-weighted signal intensity and **(b)** CBF-weighted signal intensity. # $p < .10$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$.

Chapter 7

Chronic hypertension and perfusion deficits conjointly affect disease outcome after tPA treatment in a rodent model of thromboembolic stroke

Supplementary Figure 1. The correlation between reperfusion deficiencies in the vasogenic lesion (day 1) and their definition. (a) Pearson's correlation coefficients between hypo- and hyperperfusion fractions, plotted as a function of threshold values. Shaded areas represent $\pm 95\%$ confidence interval. Dotted grey lines denote 15% threshold used for this analysis. (b) Percentages of hypo- and hyperperfused areas present within the vasogenic edematous lesion on day 1 (Figure 2(a)) using a 15% threshold. Dashed interconnected lines represent within-subject measurements, illustrating the origin of the strong negative correlation between hypo- and hyperperfusion measured in this sample.

Supplementary Figure 2. Serial coronal brain maps of ADC, T₂ and CBF, and MR angiograms from two SHR with recanalized feeding arteries but impaired reperfusion on day 1.

Supplementary Table I - RM-ANOVA – summary of linear mixed model perfusion analysis

CBF

Term	F	Df	Residual df	<i>p</i>
Strain	0	1	9.95	> 0.99
Time	77.05	2	48.51	< 0.001
ROI	11.93	1	48.02	0.001
Strain:Time	2.09	2	48.59	0.13
Strain:ROI	0.28	1	48.02	0.6
Time:ROI	14.02	2	48.02	< 0.001
Strain:Time:ROI	1.07	2	48.02	0.35

CBV

Term	F	Df	Residual df	<i>p</i>
Strain	0.18	1	9.93	0.68
Time	45.56	2	48.68	< 0.001
ROI	6.19	1	48.04	0.016
Strain:Time	0.29	2	48.79	0.75
Strain:ROI	0.73	1	48.04	0.4
Time:ROI	17.19	2	48.04	< 0.001
Strain:Time:ROI	1.21	2	48.04	0.31

MTT

Term	F	Df	Residual df	<i>p</i>
Strain	0.73	1	9.94	0.41
Time	78.75	2	48.59	< 0.001
ROI	28.02	1	48.03	< 0.001
Strain:Time	4.23	2	48.68	0.02
Strain:ROI	8.06	1	48.03	0.007
Time:ROI	2.55	2	48.03	0.089
Strain:Time:ROI	0.26	2	48.03	0.77

Supplementary Table II - Post-hoc analyses of cerebral perfusion indices before and after tPA

CBF

Strain	Time	contrast	Effect size	Estimate	SE	Resid df	t	p
SHR	Occlusion	Perilesional - Core	2.09	45.07	12.45	48.02	3.62	0.004
NR	Occlusion	Perilesional - Core	1.03	22.28	13.63	48.02	1.63	0.65
SHR	Day 1	Perilesional - Core	2.07	44.67	12.45	48.02	3.59	0.005
NR	Day 1	Perilesional - Core	1.64	35.4	12.45	48.02	2.84	0.039
SHR	Day 7	Perilesional - Core	-1.25	-26.93	12.45	48.02	-2.16	0.21
NR	Day 7	Perilesional - Core	-0.6	-12.96	12.45	48.02	-1.04	> 0.99

CBV

Strain	Time	contrast	Effect size	Estimate	SE	Resid df	t	p
SHR	Occlusion	Perilesional - Core	2.02	0.44	0.13	48.04	3.49	0.006
NR	Occlusion	Perilesional - Core	1.41	0.31	0.14	48.04	2.24	0.18
SHR	Day 1	Perilesional - Core	1.21	0.27	0.13	48.04	2.1	0.25
NR	Day 1	Perilesional - Core	1.73	0.38	0.13	48.04	2.99	0.026
SHR	Day 7	Perilesional - Core	-1.95	-0.43	0.13	48.04	-3.37	0.009
NR	Day 7	Perilesional - Core	-0.72	-0.16	0.13	48.04	-1.25	> 0.99

MTT (contrast = Strain)

Time	ROI	contrast	Effect size	Estimate	SE	Resid df	t	p
Occlusion	Core	SHR - NR	0.02	0	0.11	51.98	0.03	> 0.99
Day 1	Core	SHR - NR	1.97	0.31	0.1	50.38	3.1	0.019
Day 7	Core	SHR - NR	0.85	0.14	0.1	50.38	1.34	> 0.99
Occlusion	Perilesional	SHR - NR	-1.32	-0.21	0.11	51.98	-1.98	0.32
Day 1	Perilesional	SHR - NR	0.19	0.03	0.1	50.38	0.3	> 0.99
Day 7	Perilesional	SHR - NR	-0.1	-0.02	0.1	50.38	-0.15	> 0.99

MTT (contrast = ROI)

Strain	Time	contrast	Effect size	Estimate	SE	Resid df	t	p
SHR	Occlusion	Perilesional - Core	-2.71	-0.43	0.09	48.03	-4.7	< 0.001
NR	Occlusion	Perilesional - Core	-1.37	-0.22	0.1	48.03	-2.17	0.21
SHR	Day 1	Perilesional - Core	-1.81	-0.29	0.09	48.03	-3.13	0.018
NR	Day 1	Perilesional - Core	-0.02	0	0.09	48.03	-0.04	> 0.99
SHR	Day 7	Perilesional - Core	-1.32	-0.21	0.09	48.03	-2.29	0.16
NR	Day 7	Perilesional - Core	-0.37	-0.06	0.09	48.03	-0.64	> 0.99

Supplementary Table III - Interaction analyses - consecutive comparisons of contrasts before and after tPA

CBF

Time contrast	ROI contrast	Strain	Effect size	Estimate	SE	Resid df	t	p
Day 1 - Occlusion	Perilesional - Core	SHR	-0.02	-0.4	17.6	48.02	-0.02	> 0.99
Day 7 - Day 1	Perilesional - Core	SHR	-3.32	-71.6	17.6	48.02	-4.07	< 0.001
Day 1 - Occlusion	Perilesional - Core	NR	0.61	13.13	18.46	48.02	0.71	0.96
Day 7 - Day 1	Perilesional - Core	NR	-2.24	-48.36	17.6	48.02	-2.75	0.017

CBV

Time contrast	ROI contrast	Strain	Effect size	Estimate	SE	Resid df	t	p
Day 1 - Occlusion	Perilesional - Core	SHR	-0.8	-0.18	0.18	48.04	-0.99	0.66
Day 7 - Day 1	Perilesional - Core	SHR	-3.16	-0.69	0.18	48.04	-3.87	< 0.001
Day 1 - Occlusion	Perilesional - Core	NR	0.31	0.07	0.19	48.04	0.36	> 0.99
Day 7 - Day 1	Perilesional - Core	NR	-2.45	-0.54	0.18	48.04	-3	0.009

MTT

Strain contrast	ROI contrast	Time	Effect size	Estimate	SE	Resid df	t	p
NR - SHR	Perilesional - Core	Occlusion	1.34	0.21	0.14	48.03	1.57	0.12
NR - SHR	Perilesional - Core	Day 1	1.78	0.28	0.13	48.03	2.19	0.034
NR - SHR	Perilesional - Core	Day 7	0.95	0.15	0.13	48.03	1.16	0.25

Supplemental table IV: fractions of hypo- and hyperperfusion regressed against sensorimotor deficit score

	CBF		CBV		MTT	
Hypoperfusion (%)	0.0039 (0.64)		-0.0028 (0.81)		0.0177* (0.04)	
Hyperperfusion (%)		-0.0053 (0.60)		0.012 (0.43)		-0.028# (0.06)
Strain (hypertensive)	-0.59 (0.29)	-0.57 (0.31)	-0.66 (0.25)	-0.75 (0.20)	-0.66 (0.27)	-0.42 (0.48)
Initial ischemic volume	0.0052 (0.12)	0.0050 (0.14)	0.0066# (0.06)	0.0080* (0.03)	0.0041 (0.18)	0.0042 (0.15)
AIC	49.8	49.7	49.9	49.3	45.7	45.7
RMSE	1.39	1.38	1.42	1.38	1.12	1.03
Nagelkerke's R2	0.5	0.5	0.49	0.53	0.74	0.74
# p < 0.1, * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001						

Note: AIC = Akaike Information Criterion; RMSE = Root Mean Square Error; CBF = Cerebral Blood Flow; CBV = Cerebral Blood Volume; MTT = Mean Transit Time